

THE USE OF AUTHENTIC TEXTS IN THE PROCESS OF DEVELOPING MONOLOGUE SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract

Speaking is a type of human speech activity. Participation in the communication process involves mastering oral speech, that is, the formation of speaking skills as a type of speech competence. In the process of learning a foreign language, the development of speaking skills is focused on achieving a level of speech competencies at which the student can calmly express his own opinion/idea/thought using the means of a foreign language. It should be emphasized that both the ability to make a monologue statement and the ability to build a full-fledged dialogue in the context of a speech situation are important. In the process of learning a foreign language, authentic materials act as a resource that can serve as a model for constructing a monologue statement or provide a conceptual idea for a monologue. The article discusses the relevance of using authentic materials for the development of monologue speech skills in foreign language classes.

Keywords: monologue, monologue skills, authentic materials, authentic texts, speaking skills.

Introduction

Speaking is the main way of expressing thoughts, transmitting and exchanging information, implemented orally. E. Belyakova defines speaking as “a productive (expressive) type of speech activity, through which oral communication is carried out together with listening” [1, p. 63].

Speaking can take place in the form of monologue and dialogue. Therefore, the main speaking skills are the ability to build a full-fledged dialogue or monologue. In the process of learning a foreign language, speaking should be considered as a system of productive pronunciation, rhythmic-intonation and lexical-grammatical skills.

A monologue is a speech act performed by one person, addressing another or many people listening to it (a story/explanation by a teacher, a detailed response from a student, a report, a presentation, etc.). Thus, a monologue is the main form of expression of thoughts, ideas and positions, therefore the development of monologue speech skills is one of the basic communicative needs.

Materials and type of research

The objectives of this research are: first, to determine the essence of monologue speech skill; second, to determine the didactic potential of authentic materials; third, to develop a set of exercises for the development of monologue speech skills based on authentic materials.

Students in the 9th grade of a secondary school took part in the research.

Stages of the research:

1. Preparation of media materials and exercises for them as the basis for a subsequent experiment;
2. Development of lesson plans and conducting classes in 9th grade using journalistic materials;
3. Conducting classes using authentic materials and tasks prepared for them;

4. Systematization and analysis of results.

Research questions

Here are three research questions:

- What are the main methods for developing monologue speech skills?
- How to choose the right authentic materials for developing monologue speaking skills?
- How should you develop exercises for authentic materials to develop monologue skills?

Tools: This study presents a proper approach to developing exercises for authentic materials to develop monologue speaking skills.

Discussion

According to Cambridge dictionary a monolog is “a long speech by one person” (especially in a play, movie or television show) [2]. The characteristic features of monologue speech are composite complexity, completeness of thought, strict adherence to grammatical rules, strict logic and consistency in the presentation of the speaker’s thoughts, as well as purposefulness, continuous nature, consistency, semantic completeness, independence, expressiveness. The main characteristic feature of a monologue is the one-sided nature of the speech address. Psychological characteristics: logical coherence, semantic completeness, concreteness. Linguistic characteristics: extensiveness, varied construction of sentences, presence of connecting elements in sentences, completeness of sentences.

A monologue can be considered both a process and a product of speech activity. In each of these cases, the monologue is characterized by certain parameters. As a process, it is always purposeful, connected with communicative thinking, with general human activity, with the personality of the speaker, the speech situation, and takes place at a certain pace. As a product of monologue activity, it is always informative, productive, expressive, logically structured and holistic [3, p. 76].

An oral monologue utterance can be realized in two forms – short and extended. The short form is used to express approval, objection, surprise, reaction. These are short remarks. Typically, short monologue forms are interpreted by linguists as separate segments of more complex dialogic speech [4, p. 296]. In this vein, each line of dialogue can be interpreted as a short form of monologue. An extended monologue speech is a message, a story, an exposition, a report, an abstract, a presentation, etc. These forms are characterized by completeness of both content and form.

Monologue speech skills are “the ability to use linguistic means of a foreign language correctly, logically, communicatively, motivatedly and creatively” [5, p. 32]. Depending on what type of speech is being developed (prepared/unprepared), the choice of teaching techniques and methods depends. Unprepared monologue speech is “a situational utterance related to narrative type monologues and reasoning monologues and appearing in compositional speech forms of communication and reasoning” [6, p. 37]. Unprepared speech originates and takes shape in verbal form simultaneously with the moment of utterance. Unprepared monologue speech is characterized by initiative, unpreparedness in time, natural pace, fluency in linguistic forms.

The development of unprepared monologue speech skills is realized through the implementation of exercises in which the content, semantic side is given from the outside either in the visual (written text, pictures), or in the audio (teacher’s story, audio recording), or in a combined form (voiced video). Language material can be given in full (written text, teacher’s story), partially (key words, plan for retelling) or not given (a picture or a series of pictures without captions) [7, p. 151]. To develop prepared monologue speech various variations of authentic materials and different methods of using them can be beneficial.

Authentic materials are materials taken from original sources, characterized by the natural nature of lexical content and grammatical forms, the situational adequacy of the language means used, which illustrate cases of authentic word usage, and which are not specifically intended for educational purposes, but can be used in the teaching a foreign language process. The types of authentic materials are personal letters, anecdotes, articles, excerpts from diaries, advertising, maps, graphs and diagrams, schedules, culinary recipes, fairy tales, interviews, popular science and regional studies texts, television and radio programs, musical compositions.

In accordance with the position of A.S. Seidikenova and G.K. Zhantileuova, the relevance of using authentic materials in the teaching a foreign language process lies in their functionality [8, p.66]. Functionality refers to the orientation of such materials towards natural use, since they create the illusion of familiarity with the natural language environment.

The best sources of authentic materials to develop monologue skills of foreign language are text (literature, newspaper, magazines), music, television and videos, podcasts and radio, presentations, and speeches. In classroom the best basic and example of monologue expression could be the authentic text. According to

S. Ciornei and T. Dina the usage of authentic texts in classroom have such advantages: 1) authentic materials can serve as accurate examples of the language use by its native speakers; 2) authentic texts provide students with words and expressions used in real contexts, which allows them to be more confident in their speech when choosing words and expressions; 3) authentic materials are more informal, socially oriented and widely used [9, p.277]. The use of authentic texts in the process of teaching monologue speech ensures that students learn the real language and the specifics of using certain linguistic expressions and constructions in speech.

Authentic materials are excellent learning tools. Authentic texts are one of the means of creating a language environment for learning a foreign language. Authentic materials can, in addition to the linguistic and speech characteristics of native speakers, introduce students to the cultural features of the country of the language being studied [3]. Authentic texts provide unlimited opportunities for analyzing foreign cultural realities (from vocabulary/syntax to the characteristics of an individual’s speech behavior in a specific speech situation). Depending on the discursive context, authentic materials are characterized by the following types of authenticity: structural, lexical-phraseological, grammatical, functional, cultural, informative, situational, reactive, authenticity of national mentality, authenticity of design and authenticity of educational tasks for the text [10, p. 1202].

In the linguistic aspect, authentic texts are characterized by originality and diversity of vocabulary. They contain many pronouns, particles, interjections, words with emotional connotations, phrases designed to create associative connections, phraseological units, idioms, and speech cliches. It is also possible for sentences to be short and undeveloped, and understatement. Authentic texts can be adapted, but without compromising authenticity [4, p.37].

M. Arsentieva and N. Rungsch emphasize that text selection is a very important stage in the methodology for using authentic texts for the purposes of studying a foreign language [11, p. 178]. The texts used should satisfy the cognitive needs of students of different levels of training, enrich their worldview, ideas about the culture and history of the country of the foreign language being studied. Moreover, an interesting text can always serve as the basis for active activities in developing communication skills, in particular the ability to formulate a monologue.

Reading modern authentic texts makes it possible to study a modern foreign language, since the grammar and linguistic composition of any language are constantly transformed and developed due to new units and rules of speech behavior. Reading modern tests also allows you to develop cultural knowledge about the country of the language being studied.

The use of authentic texts in foreign language lessons has a positive impact on the development of critical thinking and universal learning activities. Authentic texts contribute to the creation of not only the necessary language environment, but also provide students with the opportunity to get acquainted with the problems,

culture, and stereotypes of the society of the foreign language being studied.

Working with authentic texts includes several stages. Reading is not the main activity. In the process of working with authentic texts, students must complete a number of tasks aimed at consolidating of read material and analyzing the content of the text, i.e. awareness of the text (direct and contextual meaning). In addition, when working with authentic texts, students actively develop translation skills and study a foreign language in the context of a lexical approach to studying a foreign language through memorizing set phrases and expressions found in the text.

Research results

During the educational experiment, based on the technological lesson map and authentic materials, 10 lessons and 2 tests were developed and conducted - introductory and final.

Lessons with students were structured as follows:

Figure 1. Experiment results

As can be seen from the results in Figure 1, the number of student errors decreased by an average of 1.5 times for each individual student. This is largely because specific aspects of the design and formulation of the monologue utterance have been worked out. Of no small importance is the format of presenting the material – visual models, which are authentic texts, contributed and simplified the process of formulating statements by students.

According to Figure 1, the proposed methodology is effective since students made significantly fewer errors in the final test. Also, lessons with authentic materials helped students remember a few of the most common speech expressions that can be used in speech to express their own opinions.

Based on the results of the experiment, at the last lesson a discussion was held with students about the need to use additional authentic materials for lessons.

- 1) explanation of new material on teaching materials;
- 2) work with authentic texts (preliminary discussion, reading the text);
- 3) performing exercises to develop monologue speech skills;
- 4) completing group/pair assignments at the end of the lesson to check mastery of the material.

During the experiment and the preparation of additional training materials, emphasis was placed on the following aspects:

- explanation of new vocabulary;
- highlighting the most important information from texts for retelling;
- study and use of speech formulas for grammatical structures to formulate a monologue expression.

During the first test, many students made mistakes in the task of formulating a written monologue statement according to a template, namely, they incorrectly used fixed expressions and speech structures.

During the discussion, students expressed and confirmed the following didactic aspects of the use of authentic texts:

- 1) Current modern texts ensured students' satisfaction in obtaining new information (information function);
- 2) Students were able to practice the skill of monologue speech, as well as other skills – reading and language guessing skills;
- 3) Students were able to expand their knowledge of new vocabulary when performing exercises to develop monologue skills based on authentic texts;
- 4) Students expanded the horizons, cultural and communicative competencies, as well as increased their motivation to learn a foreign language.

Conclusion

Monologue is one of the forms of speech utterance, which is characterized by one-pointedness, logic, and semantic completeness. To develop monologue

speech skills, it is rational to use authentic texts as an example and source of lexical and grammatical information. Authentic texts are texts that are created by native speakers for native speakers, therefore they fully reflect the linguistic picture of the foreign language being studied, as well as serve as an example of the specifics of speech activity in a foreign language.

The development of speaking skills (including monologue speech) based on developed knowledge of vocabulary involves constant systematic work on learning new vocabulary by students. One of the ways to master new vocabulary and develop students' communicative competence is to use authentic texts in the process of learning a foreign language. Working with authentic texts is an active activity of students aimed at learning new vocabulary, consolidating knowledge of grammatical forms, expanding students' horizons and regional knowledge. The use of authentic texts in English lessons develops in students such important skills as the ability to work with text, analyze, draw conclusions and generalizations. Moreover, reading modern authentic texts makes it possible to study a modern foreign language, since the grammar and linguistic composition of any language are constantly transformed and developed due to new units and rules of speech behavior.

As a result of the research, it was found that the use of authentic texts has a beneficial effect on the development of monologue speech skills.

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